

PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CLUSTERS AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM.

Makhkamov Ibrayim ifn

associate professor

Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10417126>

Abstract. In the article, the state's support measures for increasing the production efficiency of cotton-textile clusters established in our country today, when attention is being paid to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, are theoretically explained. At the same time, the proposals and conclusions that should be implemented in the formation and development of clusters in the production of competitive goods by ensuring the stable development of the economy and increasing innovative activity have been shown in the experience of foreign countries.

Key words: cotton raw material producing and processing enterprises, entrepreneurship, public-private partnership, support programs, employment, technopolis, technopark, integration, export, cluster, modernization, diversification, credit, potential, area, competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The settlement of market relations in the agricultural sector requires the use of new forms of production organization and an innovative approach to the organizational and economic mechanisms of agro-industry integration. One of the effective forms of modern approaches to agro-industry integration, the most optimal way to adapt to market relations, is agro-industry clusters in individual regions or rural areas. Therefore, the organization of clusters in the agro-industry association forms the basis of the economic policy of many countries.

The main participants of the organized agro-industrial clusters include enterprises engaged in the production of finished products (production, processing, storage, transportation, sale of agricultural products). The organizational structure of the cluster participants and the relations between them are based on the alignment of mutual interests. Such cooperation is based on voluntariness and the main focus is on accelerating the innovative development of clusters in order to increase the competitiveness of the regions. In this process, mutual integration of business entities within the cluster occurs.

From this point of view, business entities cannot be forced to join the cluster. It is the creation of opportunities for the expansion and development of their mutual relations by uniting economic entities in a cluster on the basis of cooperation. Also, favorable conditions will be created for the implementation of economic activities based on the expansion of production and technological connections, joint use of resources, purposeful consolidation of capital funds. For this, it becomes necessary to eliminate the existing obstacles in establishing this system. Then the relations between the economic units of production, distribution, exchange and consumption will take a new shape.

Also, the mutual interest of the enterprises producing and processing agricultural products will be ensured, and as a result of the integration of agriculture and industry, advanced innovative ideas will be put into practice. Today, the cooperation of enterprises that are cluster participants is organized on the basis of full market principles. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Mutual cooperation of enterprises that are participants of the cluster¹

The mutual economic relations of the enterprises within the cluster are regulated on the basis of the agreements concluded between them and this is defined in the relevant regulatory documents.

In particular, PQ-5009 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 26, 2021 "On measures to implement the tasks set in the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 in 2021" In order to "...in order to create a favorable agribusiness environment and added value chain, up to two cotton-textile clusters in one district will be allowed to operate on the basis of contracts with farms and to supply cotton raw materials to these clusters to farms." the right to voluntarily conclude futures contracts is given².

A futures contract is an agreement to buy goods at a future price based on a predetermined price.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 16, 2021 "On measures to regulate the activities of cotton-textile clusters" was adopted in order to improve and regulate mutual relations between enterprises within clusters. According to the decree, farmers working under contracts with clusters will now have the right to choose the

¹ The picture was prepared by the author using scientific literature.

² The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to implement the tasks set in the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 in 2021". The National Database of Legislative Information of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Lex.uz.. February 26, 2021.

clusters themselves. Farms are given the right to voluntarily enter into contracts with any cotton-textile cluster in their region for the supply of cotton raw materials.

According to the concluded contract, to carry out specified works on irrigation and melioration, supply seeds to farmers, provide agrotechnical services, supply fuel and lubricants, mineral fertilizers, entomologist and agronomist services. organization, installation of drip irrigation system and other related tasks are carried out by the cluster.

Also, clusters not only purchase cotton raw materials from farmers, but also provide them with advances, provide material resources and consultative support. It also guarantees loans or purchases to farmers.

All this leads to the following situation:

First, it creates an environment of free competition among cluster participants based on market mechanisms;

Secondly, the way of life of the villagers will improve due to the opportunity of the cluster participants to choose their partners voluntarily, and the income of the employees will increase;

Thirdly, agriculture, particularly cotton-textile, will be industrialized to the increase of the added value chain in the cotton-textile sector (fiber, yarn, cotton, sewing-knitting, finished products, export);

Fourthly, under the influence of the above factors, new jobs will be created and serve the growth of the regional economy and the establishment of new socio-economic infrastructures.

The above provides an opportunity for the development of mutually beneficial cooperation of small business enterprises in the network, inter-industry internal and external integration elements along with the integration of sectors - education, science and production.

However, in the course of our research and conversations with farmers, according to some information in the mass media, certain problems are highlighted in this regard. In particular, those who do not pay for the purchased cotton raw materials on time, do not support the implementation of agricultural technologies in a timely manner, buy fuels and lubricants at preferential prices and sell them to farmers at high prices. , there are also clusters that do not provide practical assistance in obtaining preferential loans. It can be seen that there are cases of misuse of privileges given to clusters, which are considered as innovations. This has a negative impact on economic relations between clusters and farmers. It is known that according to the Law, a farmer is also a cluster entrepreneur. The responsibility of both before the law should be the same, and both parties should approach the case fairly.

In turn, there are cases of non-fulfilment of some farms. Farmers receive advances for the supply of cotton raw materials, but do not fully fulfill their obligations. They try to plant high-yielding crops on a part of the cotton-growing land, and in such conditions, chemical fertilizers and chemicals are used to a high degree, as a result of which the natural structure of the land is destroyed, and the soil fertility is decreasing. Also, there are cases of planting the crops specified by the higher organizations on the plots of land owned by the farms and selling the obtained harvest, especially cotton raw materials, at the prices set by them. This causes farmers to lose interest in increasing cotton yields and increases their desire to grow other cash crops in the fields. Such a situation does not allow the rotation of the land. This also causes soil fertility to decrease.

Also, intervention of local authorities in the activities of farmers, allowing them to operate independently, i.e., to act as independent business entities that can determine how to sow crops on the land assigned to them, to whom and at what price to sell agricultural products. artificial obstacles are being placed on their activities.

Based on the above, it can be said that today the economic relationship between clusters and farmers cannot be considered as a relationship based on mutual interest and agreement, typical of the market economy.

It is necessary to develop the activities of business entities in the cluster system and to improve the economic relations between them based on the requirements of the times. Also, it is the most important task of today to give complete freedom to this field and to eliminate all the obstacles and restrictions that exist in this regard.

It also requires that farmers be given the right to freely dispose of the land areas allocated for the cultivation of cotton and grain. This will allow the land issue to be resolved legally. The resale of land ownership rights or land lease rights leads to market economy requirements.

Failure to do so will lead to a lack of confidence in clusters that are perceived as new, and people's desire for new things. However, stable development of the agricultural sector is achieved thanks to clusters. Also, socio-economic problems in our country are being solved step by step and have a positive effect on improving the well-being of the population.

President Sh. As Mirziyoyev stated in an open dialogue with the businessmen of our country on August 18 , 2023 , "...even if everyone is against it, we have started the activity of clusters and the system has shown its effectiveness" ³. It is worth mentioning that after the transition to the cluster system, the yield of cotton per hectare increased from 26 quintals to 34 quintals within six years. Up to 40 quintals were harvested in the regions. It is also worth noting that 600,000 people are currently working in cotton-textile clusters with regular income.

While there are discussions on setting the price of cotton, the information service of the Ministry of Agriculture informed Kun.uz that now the price of cotton is set based on the principles of the free market. This change is based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 26 , 2023 " On additional measures to further support the activities of cotton raw material growers ". According to the message, the price of cotton raw materials is determined in accordance with the requirements of the market economy in each region, based on the condition of the land in that region, spending on cotton cultivation, demand and supply in the market, and based on the mutual agreement of the buyer and seller. It is characterized by the fact that farmers are given the freedom to sell cotton raw materials at a mutually agreed price. Also, in order to increase the interests of farmers, up to 50 percent of the electricity used for irrigation of cotton fields through pumps will be covered from the state budget. In this regard, in protecting the legal rights and interests of private owners in the cluster system, strengthening the responsibility of the state, law enforcement and control agencies, and officials for illegal interference in the economic and financial activities of business entities should be of primary importance.

³ Raising business development to a higher level is our priority. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev speech at a meeting held in the form of an open dialogue with businessmen of our country. Official website of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.president.uz . 18.08.2023

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As can be seen from the above, our government pays special attention to solving the problems arising in the development of the cluster system. In our opinion, it is appropriate to pay attention to the following for the sustainable development of the cluster:

1. Ensuring the strict implementation of decisions, decrees and other regulatory documents related to the development of cotton-textile industries by our state, identifying the employees responsible for the implementation of the specified tasks and regularly hearing their reports on this matter, identified determining measures to eliminate deficiencies;
2. The contractual obligations between the clusters and the farmers, that is, the timely and high-quality delivery of cotton raw materials to the farmers, and the clusters to the farmers - seeds, mineral fertilizers, chemicals, fuel lubricants, modern equipment. and timely provision of such measures, strictly determining the disciplinary measures to be taken against the parties who violate the terms of the contract;
3. Studying soil fertility and its chemical and biological properties on a scientific basis, effectively organizing the fertilization of cotton planted in the regions and the use of herbicides, as well as establishing a scientifically based crop rotation system;
4. Coordinating cotton purchase prices, taking into account the price of cotton in the world market, etc., in order to increase the material interest of cotton-growing farms.

Taking into account the above, the sustainable development of cotton-textile clusters will be achieved by timely identification of problems arising in the process of development and determination of measures to solve them. This will ensure the actual implementation of the tasks defined in the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2030.

References:

1. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., & Hasanboy o'g'li, S. D. (2022). ORGANIZATION AND INCREASE OF ACTIVITY OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.
2. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., & Hasanboy o'g'li, S. D. (2022). ORGANIZATION AND INCREASE OF ACTIVITY OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.
3. Adashaliyevich, B. M., & O'g'li, I. M. (2022). Promoting sustainable development of small business. Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management, 12(4), 5-9.
4. Мухитдинов, Ш. З. (2021). ТАДБИРКОРЛИК СУБЪЕКТЛАРИДА ХАТАРЛАРНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ-УСЛУБИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 1(6), 939-943.
5. Rashidov, R. A., Hasanboeva, N. H., & ogli Otakhonov, S. M. (2021). ISSUES OF USING BANK CREDITS IN DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 2(02), 148-159.

